

UTILIZATION OF EXTRACT *Moringa oleifera* Lam. or Moringa AS A BEAUTY OR FACE TREATMENT RAW INGREDIENTS

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In this article I combine the sciences of Biology, namely Biochemistry and Plant Physiology. In this paper I explain how the relationship between the utilization of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. as raw materials that can be processed into raw materials for beauty treatments or facial treatments. One of the problems faced by society today is the fear of using chemical-based beauty products. Chemical-based beauty products have greater side effects on facial skin than beauty products made from natural ingredients such as *Moringa oleifera* Lam. *Moringa oleifera* Lam. contains rich nutrients, besides that it is also able to give good results in antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antiulcer, and antifungal treatment. In a study stated that *Moringa* leaves are proven to increase anti-aging because they contain high antioxidants and can reduce sebum gland secretion. Therefore, the extract from *Moringa oleifera* Lam, is very suitable to be used as a raw material for beauty or facial treatments at this time.

According to (Suwirman and Noli, 2022) *Moringa* leaves are one of the plants that can be used as biostimulants for other plants. *Moringa* leaves can also be used as a stimulant for the growth rate of cytokinin hormones in plants. In addition to being beneficial for the growth rate of *Moringa* leaves, it also has antioxidants in the form of quercetin which is a strong antioxidant known as a potential antioxidant, besides that, *Moringa* leaves also contain phenolic acids such as hydroxycinnamic acid, ferulic acid, cinnamic acid but in smaller amounts (Perwita, 2019). . *Moringa* leaves are the part commonly used to treat facial skin health. *Moringa* leaves are rich in mineral protein. beta carotene and antioxidant compounds that can be used as basic ingredients for organic masks (Leone, 2015; Liang 2019). According to Septiani (2012), the benefits of natural treatments tend to not have side effects like chemicals. Even if there are side effects it is not dangerous (Septiani, 2012).

Moringa leaves contain very high flavonoid compounds used as antioxidants. Antioxidants are good for health, especially skin health. Healthy skin that does not contain many diseases, either directly or indirectly. The skin can age quickly if it is often exposed to the sun, therefore a form of protection is needed on the facial skin by using beauty products (Lephant, 2016). According to (Isfianti, 2018) *Moringa* leaves contain various useful chemicals. The phytochemicals in *Moringa* are tannins, steroids and triterpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, antaquinones, and alkaloids, all of which are antioxidants. Skin damage is caused by free radicals. Free radicals can damage the skin's collagen fibers and the dermis matrix so that the skin becomes dry and aging. Catchers of the bad effects of free radicals are antioxidant compounds (Grace, 2015). According to (Thalia, 2019) the antioxidant content of *Moringa* leaves is quite high, namely 113 mg per 100 g of dried *Moringa* leaves. So, to take advantage of this *Moringa* leaf in the field of beauty, this *Moringa* leaf should be used in dry form such as a dry organic mask.

Organic masks are masks that contain organic ingredients such as fruit, vegetables, herbs, and others. Treatment using masks from organic ingredients aims to provide nutrition to facial skin, which has problems such as acne, inflammation,

or black spots, inhibits aging without causing side effects from chemicals (Perwita, 2019) inside (Widiana, 2022). According to (Odetta, 2019) to make an organic mask of Moringa leaves, only Moringa leaves are needed. The first step that must be done is to dry the Moringa leaves. Drying is done so that the water content in the leaves is absorbed. After the Moringa leaves are dry, continue by pounding the dried Moringa leaves until smooth. After being finely ground, the Moringa leaf powder is filtered with a sieve to produce a leaf powder that is softer than before and separates the coarse grains. After that, the organic mask is ready to use. How to use this organic mask is quite easy. Because this mask is dry, it needs water to dissolve it. Solution of 1 tablespoon of powder into three tablespoons of water. And the mask is ready to be applied to the face.

The theme of this paper is Utilizing Moringa Oleifera Lam Extract. or Moringa as Raw Material for Beauty or Facial Treatment. Beauty or facial treatments can be done by making organic masks based on Moringa leaf extract. Moringa leaves are rich in benefits for facial skin that can overcome facial skin problems, including helping to reduce black spots and reduce signs of premature aging. Moringa leaves in Indonesia are still not optimally used as raw materials for making organic masks. Because the Indonesian people are

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